

Lightweight and insulating façade components improving energy efficiency

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Development of innovative lightweight and highly insulating energy-efficient components and associated enabling materials for cost-effective retrofitting and new construction of curtain wall façades.

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=npk_KV84mGw

The EENSULATE project is a research project funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 programme. It gathers **13 partners from eight different European countries** (AGC Glass Europe, SAES Getters, Focchi, Università Politecnica Delle Marche, Selena, Bergamo Tecnologie, Gmina Miejska Dzierżonów, University College London, Ulster University, Evonik, UNStudio, and Fenix TNT). The consortium is led by **RINA Consulting**. The project started in August 2016 and will be concluded by May 2021—a total duration of 58 months.

The EENSULATE project has designed innovative lightweight (35 percent weight reduction compared to the currently best-performing modules), highly insulating **energy-efficient** components. Simultaneously, associated enabling materials for cost-effective retrofitting and new construction of curtain wall façades were developed. EENSULATE

represents an ambitious project, which aimed to introduce a novel unitised curtain wall system capable of meeting the market demand. The goal was an affordable (28 percent reduction of total refurbishment costs), high-performance prefabricated façade retrofitting solution with reduced weight and thickness. The project's objective was to help bring existing curtain wall buildings to 'nearly zero energy' standard and to reduce energy bills by at least 20 percent while complying with the structural limits of the original building structure and national building codes.

EENSULATE products

The EENSULATE project designed a curtain wall module that consists of two main insulating parts.

Foam

The first one is a highly insulating and environmentally friendly **material** used to produce a **mono-component** (OCF) and **bi-component** (TCF) **foam**. The TCF allows for the cost-effective automated manufacturing and insulation of the opaque part of the curtain wall module. The OCF enables a significant reduction of thermal bridging during the installation process.

Vacuum insulated glass (VIG)

The second product is a lightweight and thin double pane **vacuum insulated glass** (VIG) with innovative sealant and getter technologies and manufactured through an innovative low-temperature process, enabling the use of fully toughened glass. The VIG guarantees the insulation of the transparent part of curtain walls.

BGTEC manufactures the VIG using a tailored process that implements

innovative sealant and getter strips, ensuring the achievement of the target performance. The VIG is manufactured in two sizes:

- small-scale VIG prototypes (500x500mm)
- large-scale VIG prototypes (1000x1000mm)

The high effort by project partners ULSTER and SAES during the assembly process for the small-scale VIG prototypes (500mm x 500mm) resulted in the achievement of the project

performance goals and the definition of a reliable process protocol ready for technology transfer and for large scale production.

Two approaches were investigated for the application of the polymer edge sealant:

1. Needle dispensing by semi-automated two-axis machine loaded with sealant syringes kept at a temperature range of 60°C to 80°C.
2. Manual application of sealant-based preformed solid strips.

Figure 1: VIG sample—key components.

Demonstration

The EENSULATE products were implemented at three different demonstration sites. Two buildings located in Dzierżoniów, Poland (school building and museum), and one located in Pesaro, Italy (public library). The performance of the installed EENSULATE solutions was assessed and compared to the state-of-the-art technologies that already exist on the market, e.g. triple-glazed units (TGUs).

Public school, Dzierżoniów

The renovation intervention consisted of the full substitution of the curtain wall façade (including frame) of the school building. The selected façade is one of three façades of the overall building. The building area subjected to the refurbishment is organised as an open space where students spend their free time during breaks. In order to compare the performances of the project developed solution, two floors of the building façade were partially covered by EENSULATE modules with VIGs and the rest by the same module using a standard TGU in the frame.

Figure 2: EENSULATE façade module installation at the public school.

Museum, Dzierżoniów

The intervention and the implementation of EENSULATE glass based on VIG technology was done in a selected number of museum windows. Being a historical building, renovation works, including the ones related to windows, are subject to several and severe restrictions to preserve its artistic value. For this reason, the implementation of VIG directly in the original windows

Figure 3: EENSULATE demonstration site—Museum in Dzierżoniów.

minimised the impact of the intervention increasing the insulation capacity with a benefit for the people inside the room. This kind of operation is possible thanks to the low thickness (12.2 mm) and light weight of the VIG, perfectly adapting to the original windows and increasing their performance without changing the materials (the window frame is the original) or the aesthetic aspect.

Public library, Pesaro

San Giovanni Public Library is a complex building owned by Pesaro Municipality and is protected by the regimentation of architectural superintendence. Although Pesaro municipality is not a

project partner, they made this building available as a demonstration case of the EENSULATE project. The intervention was done by implementation of EENSULATE glass based on VIG technology in a door-window located in an area of the building organised as an open space. The VIG was installed directly in the original frame of the door-window, minimising the work carried out as well as the waste of material. The simple substitution of the glass part of the door-window with a high insulating VIG increases the thermal insulation of the window system with a consequent benefit for the visitors while not affecting the aesthetic of the building.

Figure 4: The San Giovanni Library window chosen for monitoring.

Conclusion

The design of the EENSULATE solutions for retrofitting scenarios demonstrates the wide applicability of EENSULATE components in different types of buildings with various objectives of retrofitting. Application guidelines are defined supporting the retrofitting market with EENSULATE components, as summarised below:

Retrofitting of curtain wall façade

- 1) **Façade replacement:** the EENSULATE module is applicable for the replacement of existing curtain wall façades—the school building. The EENSULATE module is a lightweight solution that does not add weight on the load-bearing structure of the building and is able to increase the energy performance. The profile colour of the EENSULATE module can be customised to meet specific architectural needs.
- 2) **Existing glass replacement:** the EENSULATE VIG is applicable for the replacement of other glazed elements in a curtain wall façade—Focchi Headquarters. The adoption of the EENSULATE VIG is possible with minor changes in curtain wall system and with the adoption of a curved profile to mitigate thermal bridging. Moving from TGUs and VIG, and vice-versa, (the school replacement strategy) proves easy application of EENSULATE VIG.

Retrofitting of windows

- 1) **Historical window:** the EENSULATE VIG is applicable for the replacement of historical glass with an improvement in energy performance without affecting the overall configuration of the windows.
- 2) **Contemporary window:** the EENSULATE VIG is applicable for the replacement of double-glazed units/ TGUs in existing windows with improvement of energy transmittance without affecting the overall configuration of the window.

PROJECT SUMMARY

The EENSULATE project aims to develop innovative, lightweight and highly insulating energy-efficient components and associated materials for cost-effective retrofitting and new construction of curtain wall façades.

PROJECT LEAD

RINA Consulting

With 160 years of experience across a wide range of industries, RINA is a multinational company that helps clients build strong, successful businesses. Through a global network of 200 offices in 70 countries, RINA supports market operators across the entire lifecycle of their projects. RINA's main areas of focus are energy, marine, transport and infrastructure, industry, and research and development.

PROJECT PARTNERS

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